

IMPLEMENTATION OF HUMAN RESOURCES MANAGEMENT IN INCREASING EFFECTIVENESS AT SDIT ASY-SYAFIYAH GARUT REGENCY

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Abstract.

This study aims to deepen and analyze the implementation and effectiveness of human resource management in the context of educational institutions in schools. This study uses a qualitative method with a descriptive approach. The data collection techniques used in this study are interviews and documentation. The validity of this research is also obtained through the source triangulation technique, which compares the information obtained by the author with the theory used. Informants in this study consisted of school principals, administrative heads, and teachers. Data analysis is carried out through data reduction, data presentation, and conclusion drawing. The results of the study show that the implementation of human resource management at SDIT Asy-Syafiiyah Kabupaten Garut has been carried out well, with a focus on four aspects; recruitment, training, compensation, and termination. The four main aspects studied by the author are in line with Schuler's theory and the opinions of the three informants studied. The results of this study are expected to contribute to the development of human resource management theory and practice, and provide useful guidance for educational institutions in improving the quality and effectiveness of human resource management.

Keywords: Effectiveness; Human Resource Management; Implementation

A. INTRODUCTION

The quality of a nation's human resources depends on its people. The higher the quality of a nation's human resources, the more advanced the country will be. This is proven by developed countries such as Japan and America which pay attention to the quality of their human resources. For example, Japan was able to rapidly improve the quality of its human resources after the second world war, this was because after the Hiroshima and Nagasaki tragedy, the Japanese government, namely Emperor Hirohito, said, "how many teachers do you have?" available?" and emphasized that "Japan will not be able to catch up with America if it does not learn."

Awareness of the quality of human resources is shown in the country to rise and develop. Human resources in the modern era today have many challenges in their management. Technological developments are the biggest example that have an impact on humans. Humans are forced to keep up with developments in order to compete in the current era of globalization. In the era Currently, humans are required to be dynamic and competitive

human beings. Without dynamic and competitive capabilities in the era of globalization, life and competition will feel difficult. The era of globalization has a positive impact on human life, but on the other hand, globalization also has a negative side to human life.

One of the prosperity of a nation is the quality of its human resources. When the quality of human resources can be improved, awareness of science will increase. The first step in improving human quality is through education. Through education, the quality of the nation's children can be realized and developed. Education is an activity of a business that aims to develop human potential to be of higher quality through learning activities. Education functions as a shaper of the face of humanity that has good moral, intellectual and human qualities and through educational activities it is hoped to produce human qualities that are able to adapt and are useful for themselves and the nation. Education plays a big role in forming good human qualities, therefore the importance of maintaining the quality of a nation's education is the most important formula in the process.

Education requires management in managing its goals and vision and mission so that they can be achieved effectively. One of them is human resource management in the education sector which is the most important factor in running other resources. Human resources play a very important role considering that only human resources have common sense in carrying out goals. Educational institutions must therefore be able to manage the recruitment, training, compensation and dismissal processes in educational activities in order to create and maintain the effectiveness and efficiency of the goals to be achieved.

Human resource management plays an important role in improving the effectiveness of human resources in schools. The human resources referred to are educational personnel which include educational unit managers, educational owners, supervisors, teachers, researchers in the field of education, developers, librarians, laboratory assistants and technicians in the field of education. The aim of implementing human resource management is to provide an effective work unit for schools.

Schools that have good quality education are a dream for parents who want to send their children to school with the hope that their children can become the nation's successors with good morals and aqidah, good knowledge, and wisdom in choosing and determining their future path in life. Quality teachers will create quality students. Therefore, schools must have criteria in selecting prospective teachers in their school recruitment so that these teachers have a professional attitude in teaching and are able to make maximum contributions to the schools they teach.

Education ultimately has several problems that arise due to the lack of quality and professionalism of teaching staff in the field of education. This is the author's basic reference for researching how to manage quality human resources. The author's problem Assuming both directly from the field and from community input regarding education, many say that the quality of teachers in several schools is still not of high quality due to a lack of awareness of educating students professionally and they still sometimes abandon their obligations as teachers and give several tasks without providing providing

information to students first, which seems to force students to find out things they don't know yet and actually hinders the efficient and effective process of students reaching their potential.

The process of achieving the required employee quality must go through several stages of screening. In general, this screening process takes the form of a selection that has been adjusted by the school according to its vision and mission. The recruitment process is the first step in finding suitable employees. After recruitment occurs according to school requirements, staff training must also be considered. This training aims to ensure that working employees understand, improve and become more professional about their work. The training aims to ensure that each employee understands and is professional in their respective positions.

One way to develop human resources in education is through the development of educational staff and the development of school principals (Rosida., 2021). The importance of schools maintaining and sharpening employee abilities. Apart from recruitment and training, compensation is also very important. This aims to maintain and appreciate the services of these employees. Compensation is an important part, because with compensation awards are given to employees. Apart from this, in maintaining the quality of human resources. Dismissals also need to be carried out, this aims to ensure that employees who do not meet the standards can be replaced by those who do. Schools' firmness in managing their own employees is an important step. Especially in maintaining and carrying out the vision and mission that will be achieved. The problems that often occur often lie with humans themselves, who sometimes make mistakes in positioning. These mistakes can have a fatal impact on the future of the school.

B. RESEARCH METHODS

The type of research that the author studied used descriptive qualitative research methods (Soegiono., 2019). The author's approach is an approach carried out using the field research method (Suharismi and Arikunto., 2011). The author obtained data based on the situations and conditions that occurred in the field by looking for meaning and not adding or changing the variables that the author studied. This research was conducted at SDIT Asy-Syafiiyah Garut Regency. Data collection was carried out through unstructured interviews and documentation. Data sources include primary sources and secondary sources. Primary sources are school principals, heads of administration, and teachers. Secondary sources are documents and various other literature that strengthen the authenticity and factuality of school data. Data analysis uses a model (Siyoto and Sodik, 2015), a series of activities for reviewing, grouping, systematizing, interpreting and verifying data so that a phenomenon has social, academic and scientific value. The reduction process is carried out to select the main and appropriate things, then data presentation is carried out, and data verification is carried out so that the validity of the data is maintained and the discussion does not run away from the intended point. Test the validity of the data using source triangulation and technical triangulation.

C. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Results

Research findings and results relating to the implementation of human resource management at SDIT Asy-Syafiiyah Garut Regency which includes recruitment, training, compensation and dismissal.

Recruitment taking place at SDIT Asy-Syafiiyah Garut Regency, based on findings from the interview and documentation process. There are findings that the author found, namely as follows: 1) the recruitment process is carried out by filing in accordance with applicable requirements and priority is given to PGSD/PGMI graduates at SDIT Asy-Syafiiyah Garut Regency, 2) after the registration is complete, the prospective teachers will be re-selected at PC Nahdatul Ulama Lewigoong District for cadre formation. 3) After the process is complete, the candidate will be directed back to SDIT Asy-Syafiiyah Garut Regency for the inauguration.

The training that took place at SDIT Asy-Syafiiyah Garut Regency, the results provided findings, namely: 1) routine training every week, 2) annual training before entering new teachings. 3) The training process is carried out offline and carried out in the hall. 4) if there are teachers or staff who cannot attend the training process, follow-up training will be carried out in the near future Compensation that took place at SDIT Asy-Syafiiyah Garut Regency, results

The findings found are as follows: 1) awards for teachers who excel, 2) prizes in the form of education by continuing their Masters for five people, 3) social assistance to teachers or staff who are experiencing disaster, 4) Umrah program for teachers and staff who excel.

The dismissal carried out at SDIT Asy-Syafiiyah Garut Regency had the following findings: 1) The dismissal was carried out in accordance with Applicable law, 2) Dismissal is carried out in accordance with the provisions in the form of not smoking, not dating, being in the process of or having entered the recruitment process in an institution, company, school or organization. 3) The stop is crosschecked again at PCM Muhammadiyah Bandar Lampung so that there are no mistakes in the process.

2. Discussion

Human resource management is a management activity that is rooted in the word manage which has the meaning of administering, arranging, implementing and administering. From the perspective of the Qur'an, management has the basic word dabbara which has the same meaning, namely managing. That matter sourced from the letter As-Sajdah aly' at 5 yl ang reads

Meaning: "He regulates (yuddabiru), affairs from heaven to earth, then (affairs) ascend to Him in one day, the amount (duration) is a thousand years according to your calculations."

The Islamic view regarding human resource management is explained in Surah Al-Baqarah verse 30, which reads:

Meaning: "Remember when your Lord said to the Angels: "Indeed, I want to make a caliph on the face of the earth." They said: "Why do you want to make (caliph) on earth someone who will cause damage to it and shed blood, even though we always glorify you by praising you and purifying you?" God says: "Indeed, I know what you do not know."

This verse explains that Allah SWT wants to make humans caliphs on earth. This means that humans are creatures who are given common sense in managing all abundant resources. Allah SWT. know better that humans have the ability to manage existing resources, including human resources.

Human Resource Management according to Cushway in Priyono (2010) defines, "part of the process that helps the organization achieve its objectives" which defines that human resources are one part of the process of achieving company goals. Meanwhile, Schuler in Priyono interprets, "Human Resource Management (HRM) is the recognition of the importance of an organization's workforce as vital human resources contributing to the goals of the organization, and the utilization of several functions and activities to ensure that they are used effectively and fairly for the benefit of the individual, the organization, and society" this definition means that human resource management is the most important factor in an organization as an achievement of the organization's goals. Management in human resource management also provides benefits for both parties, both the company and the employees themselves.

From the research findings, the author analyzed the research results at SDIT Sya-Syafiiyah Kabupaten Garut. This analysis was carried out with several facts and field data findings by comparing existing theories in human resource management. Human Resource Management, which is divided into four indicators, namely recruitment, training, compensation and dismissal, is the author's benchmark in this research. This is because these four factors are important implementation activities in maintaining quality human resources.

Recruitment

Recruitment according to the theory of Werther and Davis in Nila (2016) states that recruitment is "The process of finding and attracting applicants who meet the requirements to be hired" while according to Kasmir in Nila (2016) recruitment is "Activities to attract a number of applicants to apply to an institution". According to these two theories, recruitment is an activity to attract a number of employees in accordance with the required conditions. The Islamic view regarding recruitment is explained in Al-Qashas verse 26 which reads:

Meaning: "Because in fact the best person you can take to work (for us) is someone who is strong and trustworthy."

The results of research on recruitment found at SDIT Sya-Syafiiyah Kabupaten Garut are generally in accordance with the steps in the recruitment process. In Wether and Davis' theory in Nila (2016) the recruitment process must be in accordance with the desired requirements in selection. This is in accordance with existing theory, by assessing the

needs aspect in selection. The recruitment process is an important asset because it directly carries out the school's vision and mission activities. **Training**

Training according to Wexley in Genot (2017) is "Training and development are terms referring to planned efforts designed to facilitate the acquisition of relevant skills, knowledge and attitudes by organization members. Development focuses more on improving the decision making and human relations skills and the presentation of a more factual and narrow subject matter". Wexley and Yulk's opinion explains that training and development is something that refers to related things with planned efforts carried out to achieve mastery of the skills, knowledge and attitudes of employees or members of the organization. Development is more focused on improving skills in decision making and human relations.

The training process that took place at SDIT Asy-Syafiiyah Garut Regency, the results provided findings, namely: 1) regular training every week, 2) annual training before entering new teachings. 3) The training process is carried out offline and carried out in the hall. 4) if there are teachers or staff who cannot attend the training process, follow-up training will be carried out in the near future. Based on these findings, the author analyzes that these findings are in accordance with Wexley's theory in Genot (2017) where training is a development process that refers to the main things in the needs of an organization or company. These findings provide an illustration that SDIT Asy-Syafiiyah Garut Regency pays attention to the training carried out so that it meets the main objectives of the school. The training process is an important aspect in developing teachers and staff to comply with the vision and mission of SDIT Asy-Syafiiyah Garut Regency.

Compensation

Compensation according to Schuler in Hakim (2009) "in principle rewards can be divided into two, namely intrinsic rewards and extrinsic rewards. Intrinsic rewards are rewards that employees receive for themselves while extrinsic rewards include direct compensation, indirect compensation and non-monetary rewards". Compensation is also a way of appreciating employee performance. According to Siagian in Ameliawati (2015), "A sense of justice can make employees satisfied with the compensation they receive." Compensation These findings provide an analysis that is in accordance with Schuler's theory in Hakim (2009) that compensation is an activity of giving appreciation for services that have been provided. The author's analysis of the theory and data findings is in accordance with what was carried out. Providing compensation is an important aspect to foster enthusiasm for work. Giving gifts in the form of rewards for the services they provide will create a feeling of happiness in itself. SDIT Asy-Syafiiyah Garut Regency pays attention to providing appropriate compensation.

Dismissal

Dismissal according to law. No. 13 of 2003 means that dismissal or termination of employment is the termination of the employment relationship due to certain reasons which result in the end of the rights and obligations between workers and employers. Meanwhile, according to Moekijat in Siti, it means that "Dismissal is the termination of an

employee's working relationship with a company organization". According to Manulang in Sri Zulhartiti, the term employment termination can provide several meanings, namely: 1) Termination, namely the termination of the employment relationship due to the completion or expiration of the agreed employment contract.

At the end of the contract, if there is no agreement between the employee and management, the employee must leave his job. 2) Dismissal, namely the termination of the employment relationship because the employee commits a predetermined disciplinary violation. For example: employees make mistakes, such as consuming alcohol or psychotropic drugs, being violent, committing crimes, damaging factory work equipment. 3) Redundancy, namely termination of employment because the company is developing using new technology machines, such as: the use of industrial robots in the production process, the use of heavy equipment that is sufficient to be operated by one or two people to replace a number of workers. This has an impact on reducing the workforce. 4) Retrenchment, namely termination of employment relations associated with economic problems, such as economic recession, marketing problems, so that companies are unable to provide wages to their employees.

These findings provide analysis results that SDIT Asy-Syafiiyah Garut Regency has carried out dismissals in accordance with applicable laws and regulations. According to Law. No. 13 of 2003 provides dismissal regulations that state that dismissal is carried out for certain reasons which result in the end of the rights and obligations between workers and employers. This dismissal process needs to be paid attention to because mistakes in carrying out the dismissal will have quite significant impacts. SDIT Asy-Syafiiyah Garut Regency has paid attention to the dismissal process by cross-checking the dismissal decision and the policies that have been established.

D. CONCLUSION

After the writer gets the information and analyzes the information. The author concludes that the implementation of Human Resources Management at SDIT Asy-Syafiiyah Garut Regency has gone very well in its implementation. The author analyzes and compares these things based on theory, laws, shared information, documentation, and the results of analysis in the field. The results of research regarding the Implementation of Human Resources Management at SDIT Asy-Syafiiyah Garut Regency can be concluded as follows:

Recruitment

SDIT Asy-Syafiiyah Garut Regency has a need for recruiting PGSD teachers, the recruitment process is carried out through two selections, namely PCNU Lewigoong cadre formation and forwarded to the school, the main requirements needed are not smoking, not dating, S1 graduate, GPA not below 3.0, capable read the Koran well. The obstacle that occurs is the difficulty of finding PGSD teachers who suit your needs.

Training

Training at SDIT Asy-Syafiiyah Garut Regency has two routine programs, annual and weekly. The program takes the form of teacher training, training on the integration of Islamic values in teaching, excellent service training, presentation training, excellent service training, training in making learning equipment.

Compensation

Compensation at SDIT Asy-Syafiiyah Garut Regency, Masters education or to continue studying for a Bachelor's degree in PGSD/PGMI, compensation for those who want to get married, are hit by a disaster, are sick, economic assistance, Umrah for five people, and compensation for additional hours.

Dismissal

Dismissal at SDIT Asy-Syafiiyah Garut Regency has a policy, namely warning letters one to three, where the rules include no smoking, dating, criminal acts that are against state law, and also other rules apart from personal mistakes such as staff or teachers having been accepted into the company, CPNS or other things that allow moving from SDIT Asy-Syafiiyah Garut Regency.

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